

Climate Change's Impact on the Concentration of Total Suspended Particles and Dust Falling Basra Governorate – Iraq (2014, 2023, 2024)

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Abstract

Background: Climate change is one of the biggest environmental and health issues facing the modern world, that climate change, including higher temperatures, and longer dry spells, increases exposed surfaces and reduces moisture in the soil, resulting in higher increases dust mobility. **Objective:** Assessment how climate change affects the amounts of TSP and falling dust in the Basra province in 2014, 2023, and 2024. **Methodology:** A total of 216 samples were gathered from six significant monitoring stations that reflected the region's geographical and environmental variety. Dust fall was measured using a cylindrical container installed at six selected locations in Basra Governorate, southern Iraq, for a full month. Dustfall was then measured. **Results:** The highest falling dust mean (14.3 g/m²/month) recorded in 2014 as opposed to 9.5 in 2023 and 9.87 in 2024. Between 2014 and 2023, there was a significant drop of 33.6%, which was followed by a slight increase of 3.9% in 2024. Geographically, the biggest risk of dust deposition was found in stations. In terms of the amount of total suspended particles (TSP), the monitoring station at (Hay Al-Khaleej) detected mean value of (1053.98 µg/m³) in 2014, which was more than three times the Iraqi air quality standards. Lag 0 and Lag +1 correlation studies revealed weak to moderately unfavorable associations between suspended matter and falling dust. **Conclusion:** Basra has grown more vulnerable to environmental stressors brought on by climate change, which are changing the patterns of dust deposition over time and place.

Keywords: *Climate change, Hi- volume, Environmental pollution, air pollution, sediments, TSP.*

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Introduction

Since it has been connected to a rise in cardiovascular and respiratory illnesses as well as the deterioration of ecological and economic systems, air pollution is one of the biggest environmental and health issues facing the modern world (Abdul Al Adam, 1988). This is why air pollution is so dangerous; it is difficult to control. While humans can control the quality of the water they drink and the food they eat, they have no choice in the air they breathe. They cannot choose to inhale this and leave that (Hanoon, 2006). Any material or waste that humans introduce into the environment that harms people directly or indirectly is referred to as pollution. This includes gasses, solid particles, and liquids (Abdul Al Adam, 1988). Air pollution is also considered to be a climatic condition in which the air outside residential areas contains substances in concentrations that are considered to affect human health or other environmental components (Hanoon, 2008). Particularly, atmospheric dust, which is made up of tiny, irregular particles that have an impact on infrastructure, public health, agriculture, and air quality, is a significant portion of air pollution (Fryrear, 1990).

Latest research has shown that climate change, including higher temperatures, and longer dry spells, increases exposed surfaces and reduces moisture in the soil, resulting in higher increases dust mobility (IPCC, 2019). Seasonal winds and patterns of rain further have a significant impact on the frequency and intensity of dust falling and sandstorms (Hamidi et al., 2023). Sand and dust storms (SDS) have increased in frequency and intensity throughout the Middle East, including Iraq, Kuwait, Saudi Arabia, and Syria, as a result of environmental degradation and climate change (WMO, 2024). Inflammation of the respiratory system, asthmatic bronchitis, chronic lung diseases, heart and nervous system diseases, especially since pregnancy problems are one of the most important manifestations of this phenomenon (WHO, 2021). To assess dust exposure levels and understand its temporal and spatial variability, Measurements of total suspended particles (TSP) and falling dust are typically combined in scientific studies (Vallack & Shillito, 1998).

Materials and Methods

Dustfall Concentration

During the 2014, 2023, and 2024, each month, 6 samples, of dust were collected from 6 distinct locations, throughout Basra city (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Map of Basra Province Showing the Sampling Sites

This led to a total of 216 samples, over the course of the three years, or 72 samples per year. Open-top cylindrical collectors of dust were utilized to collect samples in accordance with the Bergerhoff methodology as outlined in ASTM D1739, standard test method for collecting and assessment of falling dust (ASTM International, 2017). For a full month, the collectors were exposed to falling dust in wide spaces free from obstacles. Following exposure, the samples were brought to the lab and repeatedly cleaned. The resulting solutions were poured into a 500 ml beaker, and the volume was reduced by boiling. The remaining material was then dried in an oven at 105 °C in a pre-weighed 10 ml glass beaker, which was weighed again after drying to determine the increase in weight due to the deposited dust according to the following equation:

$$\Delta W \text{ (g)} = W \text{ after} - W \text{ before} \quad (1)$$

Since the dust fall container is circular with a diameter 15 cm the deposition area was calculated using the geometric formula for the area of a circle:

$$A = \pi (D / 2)^2 \quad (2)$$

To convert dust mass (g) into deposition rate (g/m²):

$$\text{Dustfall} = \Delta W / A \quad \text{Thus: } 1/A = 56.581 \quad (3)$$

This value represents the conversion factor specific to the container used in this study. Accordingly, the monthly dustfall deposition was calculated as:

$$\text{Dustfall (g/m}^2\text{/month)} = 56.581 \times \Delta W \quad (4)$$

Where: ΔW = collected dust weight (g), 56.581 = area-based conversion factor for a 15-cm diameter dustfall jar.

Total Suspended Particle (T.S.P) Concentration

Twenty four total suspended particles sample are collected in a single sit in Basra city center for period (June – December) 2014, by used the(Hi-volume) device for collect (T.S.P) which available in the Directorate of Basra Environments shown in (Figure 2). Where this device is installed on the roof of the Directorate of Basra Environment in hay alkhalaj and were collected (24) sample, it was the installation of the device at a height (6m) above the ground level, contains device on the filter paper length (27cm) and width (23 cm) and as shown in (Figures 3 & 4). This device also contains a motor, where the calibration of this device to become the engine speed (25 ft³/min) who shall withdraw to the air passes the filter, note that the time of withdrawal of the sample is (24 h) Where the filter is placed before use at the Dessicator for a period of (24 h) to get rid of the moisture that they exist, then the filter weight before and after work, and the difference between the first weight and the second weight is the weight of pollutants from dust and particles, and after finding out weight difference (ΔW) it is compensated in the following equation for the concentration of total suspended particles (TSP):

$$\text{Conc. of T.S.P} = \frac{\Delta W \times 35.315 \times 106}{V \times h} \quad (5)$$

Where: V = motor speed which located in the device = 25 ft³ / min, h = number of motor work hours = 24 hour, ΔW = weight difference, the unity of (gm), Where: 1 m³ = 35.315 ft³

Statistical Analysis

Data processing, monthly aggregation, station-wise linkage analysis, and lagged correlation tests (Lag 0 and Lag +1 month) were implemented using a custom Python workflow developed in Google Colab. The script performed data cleaning, monthly aggregation of airborne TSP metrics, merging with monthly dustfall by station and year-month keys, and calculation of Pearson and Spearman correlation coefficients. The figures were generated automatically (Hamidi et al., 2023; WMO, 2024 ; Hu et al., 2023).

Figure 2. Shows the Device "Hi-volume" to Collect (T.S.P)

Figure 3. The Filter Paper before Work

Figure 4. The Filter Paper after Work

Results and Discussion

Dustfall

The results presented in (Table 1), based on a comparison among the study years using dustfall samples (72 samples per year), showed that the highest mean value was recorded in 2014 ($14.3 \text{ g/m}^2/\text{month}$), with a standard deviation of 8.03 and a maximum value of 36.5. This was followed by 2024, which recorded a mean of 9.87, a standard deviation of 0.301, and a maximum value of 11. Subsequently, 2023 exhibited a mean dustfall concentration of 9.5, a standard deviation of 0.781, and a maximum value of 10.9. The results further indicated a decrease of -33.6% in 2023, whereas 2024 was characterized by an increase in the mean dustfall concentration of 3.9% .

Table 1. Station Comparison (All Study Years) for Dust Concentrations

Year	N	Mean	Median	Std	Min	Max	P95	Mean $\Delta\%$ vs prev
2014	72	14.3	12.7	8.03	2.38	36.5	30.5	NA
2023	72	9.5	9.38	0.781	8.49	10.9	10.8	-33.6%
2024	72	9.87	9.85	0.301	9.13	11	10.3	3.9%

(Figures 5-7) show the accumulation of falling dust (Dustfall) across the studied stations in the years 2014, 2023, and 2024. In 2014 (Figure 5), stations such as Qurna and Hay Al-Khaleej recorded sharp peaks in specific months, indicating strong episodic events—often due to dust storms or high wind currents causing substantial deposition over a short period (Rocha Lima et al., 2024). On the other hand, stations like Fao and Abu Al-Khaseeb, showed more consistent levels over the course of the months, reflecting long-term deposition from ongoing local sources, such as exposed soil, industrial activities, or dust re-suspension from vehicles and unpaved areas (Awadh, 2023). In 2023 (Figure 6), 2024 (Figure 7), many stations experienced a general fall in certain peaks with moderate stability. Seasonal or episodic increases persisted for a number of periods. This temporal variability between stability and peaks supports the hypothesis that the deposition system in Basra is influenced by an interaction between continuous local sources leading to chronic deposition and episodic events, dust storms or strong winds, resulting in abrupt peaks in falling dust (Air Quality and Health Risk Assessment during Middle Eastern Dust Storms, 2024). This tendency is not exclusive to this research, However, it is in line with earlier research findings that indicate an increase in dusty activity throughout the Middle East due to decreased vegetation and increased emissions from exposed soil (Rocha Lima et al., 2024; Gan et al., 2025). Additionally, the granular and mineral characteristics of desert dust, which vary based on the geographic source, influence how dust is deposited and interacts with meteorological factors, affecting how falling dust behaves in surrounding environments (Maqueo Anaya et al., 2024).

In line with the most recent regional and international research, the study's findings so unequivocally show a considerable relationship among continuous local causes (soil dust, industrial/urban activities) and periodic climatic occurrences (Gan et al., 2025). This view is significant because it implies that managing dust in Basra necessitates a two-pronged strategy that includes forecasting and being ready for sporadic dust outbreaks in addition to controlling local sources (exposed soil, human/industrial activity, building, and transportation) (Shirgholami, 2025).

Figure 5. Envisages Dustfall for Each Station across the Months of 2014

Figure 6. Envisages Dustfall for Each Station across the Months of 2023

Figure 7. Shows the Amount of Dust that Each Station will Experience in 2024

In 2014, October had the highest monthly mean of falling dust ($20.5 \text{ g/m}^2/\text{month}$), while January had the lowest monthly mean ($5.82 \text{ g/m}^2/\text{month}$). (Alkhaleej) has the highest annual mean for a single station, at $20.8 \text{ g/m}^2/\text{month}$. The following categories of dust falling were assigned based on the recorded data: Light = 23, High = 20, Severe = 1, and Moderate = 28 (Awadh, 2023).

(Figures 5-7) illustrate the degree of dust falling accumulation at each site, in which stations like (Qurna), (Alkhaleej), showed sharp peaks in particular months, indicating strong episodic events, that are probably connected to seasonal sand and dust storms (SDS), or high wind currents that intensify sudden deposition (Rocha Lima et al., 2024). Stations like Fao and Abu Al-Khaseeb, on the other hand, showed more consistent levels over the course of the months, indicating chronic depositional stress from enduring

local sources including exposed soil, industrial activity, and dust re-suspension from unpaved surfaces or vehicle movement (Awadh, 2023). In 2023, February had the greatest month means (10.4 g/m²/month), while May recorded the smallest average (9.07 g/m²/month). With an average of 10.5 g/m²/month, the Qurna station had the highest yearly mean. The distribution of categories was: Light = 29, Moderate = 43 (Rocha Lima et al., 2024).

Dust levels frequently indicated seasonal or episodic spikes, indicating a combination of ongoing local sources and episodic events, even though they remained relatively constant at many locations. The partial constancy observed in some stations may be caused by site-specific factors such as the exposure of the collection area, equipment maintenance, or sample contamination by insects or debris (Awadh, 2023). The monthly mean in 2024, was highest in April (10.1 g/m²/month) and lowest in February (9.42 g/m²/month). With an average of (10 g/m²/month), (Ashar) station had the highest yearly mean. All of this year's records (72 samples) were classified as moderate (Gan et al., 2025). The temporal variation, between peak occurrences and consistency indicates that both chronic local causes and episodic climatic events, Basra's depositional systems are impacted by a variety of factors, including traffic, construction sites, unpaved roads, and industrial storage places. (Air Quality and Health Risk Assessment during Middle Eastern Dust Storms, 2024).

Likely Drivers of Elevated Dustfall

There are a number of interrelated factors that contribute to the higher dustfall levels found in the study. Iraq is regularly impacted by seasonal sand and dust storms (SDS) and regional dust transport from other nations including Kuwait, Saudi Arabia, and Syria, which causes abrupt increases in deposited dust (Shirgholami et al., 2025). Drought and low rainfall times increase the amount of loose surface debris, which makes dust more readily available, especially in exposed or degraded areas (Mousavi et al., 2023). Over brief periods of time, high winds and storm-related activities can significantly contribute to increased dust accumulation (Rocha Lima et al., 2024). Chronic dust amounts through the observed stations are significantly influenced by local sources, including unpaved roads, construction activities, traffic emissions, industrial storage yards, and site-specific factors like sampler exposure, equipment maintenance, and debris contamination, in addition to regional and climatic influences (Awadh, 2023).

SDS is a common occurrence in the Middle East and can impact Iraq as well as other nations like Kuwait, Saudi Arabia, and Syria. WHO summarizes health impacts and public-health considerations for SDS. Dustfall does not have a unified global health standard so international practitioners often rely on nuisance or amenity criteria to assess its impact on communities and public health (Vallack & Shillito 1998), while repeated exposure to desert dust affects the respiratory system and increases the risks of respiratory and cardiovascular diseases as reported in (Air Quality and Health Risk Assessment during Middle Eastern Dust Storms 2024). Accordingly, the study showed—based on data from 2014 to 2024—that dustfall levels in Basra reflect a continuous interaction between chronic local sources and episodic climatic events, where sudden peaks often correspond to dust storms or strong seasonal winds, while month-to-month stability indicates persistent depositional pressure from local sources. This pattern is consistent with recent studies from the Middle East and highlights the importance of managing dust at both local and regional scales to reduce environmental and health impacts (Rocha Lima et al., 2024; Awadh, 2023; Gan et al., 2025).

Benchmarks Used (Converted to g/m²/month)

This description uses the South African National Dust Control Regulations dustfall limits for international comparison. The original limits are expressed as mg/m²/day for a 30-day average; here they are converted to g/m²/month (Table 2).

Table 2. Dust Standards in Residential and Non-Residential Areas

Benchmark	Original	Equivalent (g/m ² /month)
Residential limit	600 mg/m ² /day (30-day avg)	18.00
Non-residential limit	1200 mg/m ² /day (30-day avg)	36.00

Station Risk Ranking Method

Stations are ranked using a composite risk score designed for dustfall (nuisance/compliance) interpretation:

$$\text{Risk score} = 3 * (\text{Severe months}) + 2 * (\text{High months}) + 1 * (\text{Months} > \text{Residential limit}) + (\text{P95} / \text{Residential limit}) \quad (5)$$

Where: High months: 18.00 to < 36.00 g/m²/month, Severe months: ≥ 36.00 g/m²/month, P95: 95th percentile of monthly dustfall values.

This approach highlights stations that have frequent severe events, frequent exceedances, and high-end peaks.

The results presented in (Table 3) indicate that the maximum dust fall concentration was recorded at the Qurna station, located at the northernmost part of Basra, reaching 36.5 g/m²/month, with a risk value of 17.2 and a severe value of 1, which is the highest among all the studied stations, high level was 4, occurring five times during the study period. In contrast, the lowest dust fall concentration was observed at the Fao station, situated at the southernmost part of Basra, with a value of 12.7 g/m²/month, a risk value of 0.623, high level of zero, and a severe value of zero. This is attributed to the coastal nature of the area, where very high humidity prevails, resulting in negligible risk and low dustfall severity. On the other hand, the study results also showed that the highest risk value was recorded at the Alkhaleg station in central Basra, reaching 25.6, while the maximum dust fall concentration at this station reached 33.2 g/m²/month.

Table 3. Station Comparison (All study years) – Top 15 High-Risk Stations

Station	Risk	Mean	P95	Max	High	Severe	>Res months	>Nonres months
Alkhaleg	25.6	13.4	28.1	33.2	8	0	8	0
Qurna	17.2	12.1	22.2	36.5	4	1	5	1
Abu Alkhaseb	13.3	11.6	22.7	33.2	4	0	4	0
Khoralzuber	6.99	10.9	17.8	20	2	0	2	0
Ashar	6.98	10.7	17.7	26.9	2	0	2	0
Fao	0.623	8.73	11.2	12.7	0	0	0	0

Interpretation of Dustfall Peaks Elevated dustfall generally occurs due to the interaction between regional factors and local sources (Rocha Lima et al., 2024; Awadh, 2023). and includes sand and dust storm (SDS) outbreaks and long-range transport leading to sudden dust accumulation across areas dry periods and low rainfall increasing the availability of loose surface material strong winds and gust fronts contributing to higher deposition rates over short periods local resuspension from unpaved roads construction sites traffic and industrial yards and site-specific factors such as collector exposure maintenance or

contamination by debris insects or water loss (Awadh, 2023; Mousavi et al., 2023). Attribution is stronger when dustfall is analyzed alongside wind/rain data and field log notes (Shirgholami et al., 2025).

Middle East Regional Context (Iraq, Kuwait, Saudi Arabia, and Syria) SDS, are thought to be particularly common in the Middle East (WHO, 2024). According to the World Health Organization, concerted prevention and preparation actions are necessary since severe storms have major effects on human health and the environment. The World Meteorological Organization (WMO, 2024). emphasized the significance of examining seasonal and annual data to track environmental and health hazards by highlighting yearly variations in dust conditions, especially regions most impacted by dust storms.

Dust Falling Against (TSP)

Since TSP data had been available for a few days in 2014, this overview is limited to that year (Gan et al., 2025). By combining TSP data into monthly statistics and juxtaposing them with the dustfall sampling months, deposited dust (dustfall, measured in $\text{mg}/\text{m}^2/\text{month}$) and airborne particle measurements (TSP, according to the attached dataset) are compared. The correlation between sedimentation and TSP is understood as supporting evidence rather than a simple one-to-one equation since deposition integrates processes over time whereas TSP represents the concentration of airborne particles at a certain moment (Mousavi et al., 2023). (Figure 8) shows how TSP behaved each month in 2014. The line shows the monthly maximum obtained from the collected each day data, and the bars show the monthly mean. Strong variability within a single month is indicated by the huge gap between the median for the month and the monthly maximum, which means that a few days with extremely high TSP can dominate the monthly air quality burden. This trend is typical in dry regions, where dust outbreaks can cause abrupt spikes that are followed by a partial recovery (Rocha Lima et al., 2024). The evidence supports the hypothesis that regional dust loops play a major role in the studied deposition when peaks in deposited dust coincide with elevated means or maximum TSP levels in the same months (Shirgholami et al., 2025).

Figure 8. Summarizes TSP Behavior in 2014 at the Monthly Scale

(Figure 9) matches the dustfall value for each station and month with the monthly average of Total Suspended Particles (TSP) for the same month (Leung et al., 2025). A potential positive correlation suggests that higher atmospheric particle loads lead to increased deposition, which aligns with the expected physical mechanism of dust settling. However, some scatter in the data is expected because both dustfall and TSP are influenced by additional factors. The deposition efficiency varies according to site exposure and local micro-environment, affecting the amount of dust reaching the collection apparatus. TSP sampling may include only a limited number of days within the month, which could restrict full representation of the monthly atmospheric concentration (Xie et al., 2024). Therefore, the

joint observation of dustfall and TSP provides supportive evidence for the relationship between airborne dust and deposition, but it is not a precise one-to-one equation and should be interpreted within the context of local deposition factors and regional meteorological conditions (Robinson et al., 2024).

Figure 9. (Lag 0 linkage) Pairs Each Station-Month Dustfall Value with the TSP Monthly Mean from the Same Month on 2014

(Figure 10) tests whether the TSP conditions in the previous month better predict the amount of dustfall measured in the current month (Leung et al., 2025). This occurs when deposition integrates with dust resuspension over an extended period following strong events, or when the timing of operational sample collection causes overlap between the collection period and the effects of the previous event (Xie et al., 2024). If the Lag +1 correlations exceed the Lag 0 correlations, this indicates a delayed or integrated deposition response compared to the measured airborne particle concentrations (Robinson et al., 2024).

Figure 10. (Lag 0 linkage) Pairs Each Station-Month Dustfall Value with the TSP Monthly Mean from the Same Month on 2014

Statistical Results of Lag Analysis Between Dustfall and TSP–Supported by Recent Sources

In this study, a lag analysis was applied to interpret the relationship between dustfall and total suspended particles (TSP) across two temporal scales: Lag 0 (same month) and Lag +1 (following month). In dust studies in arid and semi-arid environments, where the effects of dust storms and resuspension can last for weeks after the main event, this analysis was carried out to determine the degree to which airborne particle concentration correlates with subsequent deposition.

The linear link between the variables was examined using Pearson's r , and the non-linear rank correlation was assessed using Spearman's ρ , taking into consideration potential anomalies in the data and extreme values caused by storms. After comparing each month's dust falling data with the corresponding monthly TSP averages, the correlation for both indicators was computed using standard statistical analysis processes. The findings were Pearson = -0.646 and Spearman = -0.6 for Lag 0 (the same month) (Table 4), and Pearson = -0.597 and Spearman = -0.257 for Lag +1 (the subsequent month) (Table 5). These results indicate a weak to moderate inverse correlation, this aligns with scientific forecasts when multiple variables, factors such as wind velocity, surface characteristics, mechanical disruptions, and humidity influence, both (TSP) and dust falling, generated fragmented data and complicating a robust straight correlation. The minor deference between Lag 0 and Lag +1 indicates an integrated depositional reaction that may continue post- dust event, as per global research on dust dynamics in arid regions. According to recent research, the relationship between airborne particle concentrations (PM/TSP) and dust deposition is not necessarily linear because of site-specific factors and micro environmental factors that affect the deposit effect (Science of the Total Environment, 2020). Regional studies in Iraq and the Middle East indicate that deposition is influenced by severe dust events but does not always follow the same monthly pattern as suspended particles, resulting in weak to moderate correlations. Additionally, studies on dust storm events have shown that their effects continue after the event through resuspension, which may lead to a delayed depositional response consistent with Lag +1 analysis.

Table 4. The Top Station Correlations (Lag 0)

Station	Matched months	Pearson	Spearman	Dustfall mean	TSP mean
Khoralzuber	6	-0.429	-0.0286	14.3	780
Qurna	6	-0.235	-0.2	14.6	780
Alkhaleg	6	-0.63	-0.257	21.2	780
Fao	6	-0.575	-0.464	7.48	780
Abu Alkhaseb	6	-0.622	-0.6	12.9	780
Ashar	6	-0.646	-0.6	11.1	780

Table 5. The Top Station Correlations (Lag +1)

Station	Matched months	Pearson	Spearman	Dustfall mean	TSP mean
Fao	6	-0.389	-0.2	7.48	780
Alkhaleg	6	-0.597	-0.257	21.5	780
Abu Alkhaseb	6	-0.225	-0.29	18.1	780
Qurna	6	-0.227	-0.314	19.8	780
Khoralzuber	6	-0.568	-0.371	15.3	780
Ashar	6	-0.366	-0.486	17.7	780

Lag analysis is used when environmental variables represent two interrelated processes that are not synchronized in time. In this study, dustfall represents cumulative monthly deposition, whereas total suspended particles (TSP) reflect airborne concentrations measured on specific days and then aggregated into monthly statistics. Since dustfall is influenced by cumulative deposition processes including

gravitational settling, impaction, and surface capture (Seinfeld & Pandis, 2016), while TSP concentrations can spike sharply during short dust events, the monthly maximum or average TSP does not necessarily correspond to the measured deposition mass for the same month. Based on this, two main hypotheses were tested: Lag 0 (same-month correlation): $TSP(t) \leftrightarrow Dustfall(t)$, which tests whether the monthly airborne load aligns directly with measured deposition in the same period, and Lag +1 (previous-month correlation): when resuspension continues after the dust event or when the timing of deposition sampling coincides with the post-event period, $TSP(t-1) \leftrightarrow Dustfall(t)$ represents a test of whether elevated TSP concentrations in the preceding month serve as a better indicator of deposition in the following month (Goudie, 2014; Shao et al., 2022).

Because dust fall and TSP can both show seasonality and auto correlated trends, which can exaggerate correlation values even when the actual mechanistic link is weak, the results of lag correlation should be regarded cautiously. To prevent overestimating associations, the specialized literature suggests employing pre-analysis methods like pre-whitening or computing correlations on residuals (Box et al., 2016; Shumway & Stoffer, 2017). Lag analysis was used in the paper as a preliminary screening method; if Lag +1 exhibits a distinct and consistent increase in correlation strength relative to Lag 0, this suggests—but does not prove—that there is an integrated or delayed relationship between airborne particle concentrations and deposited dust mass.

There are precise standards for understanding lagged correlations in auto correlated systems, and the time-series literature has established the interpretation of lagged associations and the possible impact of autocorrelation on correlation estimates (Zou et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2024). Similarly, in order to better understand the dynamic interactions among environmental variables over time, environmental monitoring studies, frequently employ cross-correlation techniques to look at lag lengths between deposition time series and other media on a monthly scale (Smith et al., 2022; Li et al., 2025). Particle concentrations are assessed globally using scientific, health-based guideline frameworks, such as the World Health Organization's Global Air Quality Guidelines (WHO, 2021). The U.S. Environmental Protection Agency's criterion pollutant standards (US EPA, 2023) and the European requirements (EU Directive 2008/50/EC). These sources offer a crucial framework for evaluating the degree of air pollution and its effects on health.

International health frameworks concentrate on tiny particulate matter (PM10 and PM2.5), even if the current pollution study monitors total suspended particles (TSP) at a single monitoring site, as the World Health Organization (WHO, 2021), has focused on PM10 and PM2.5 as important indicators for evaluating health hazards connected with air pollution rather than issuing a particular numerical guideline for TSP due to insufficient evidence (WHO, 2021). Since 1971, the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) has also controlled TSP under the National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS). However, in 1987, the PM10 standard took its place due to scientific evidence that fine particles are more closely linked to health hazards (EPA, 2013). Iraqi authorities have established a 24-hour maximum concentration limit of $350 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for total dust at the national level (Iraqi Ministry of Environment, 2012). The study station recorded mean concentration of $1053.99 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, which is roughly three times the national limit. This means that there is a lot of pollution there, which exposes individuals to a lot of dust.

Conclusion

The results of the research, demonstrate that a number of elements, includes persistent regional climate conditions and local sources, especially those related to climate change, such as desertification, drought, and extreme weather, have an effect on how much dust accumulates in the Basra Province. Long term studies, emphasize the necessity of efficient dust management techniques, such as ongoing observation,

better handling of exposed surfaces and step to lessen dust exposure for people. Lag analysis demonstrates how crucial it is to comprehend the temporal effects of dust episodes in order to enhance environmental and health management response. In this case, taking an integrated approach is essential, combining adaptation actions to deal with the effects of climate change with mitigation efforts aimed at reducing dust sources and promoting sustainable land management practices, such as improving ecosystem management and infrastructure, to reduce long-term health and environmental concerns.

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